

TURNkey - Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

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Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D3.10

Demonstrator and accompanying report of the estimation of seismic magnitude using citizen information from smartphone apps (EEW) – (Joint Deliverable with RISE project)

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GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismology Centre
FAME	Felt Area for Magnitude Estimate
MLP classifier	Multi-Layer Perceptron classifier
PCA	Principal Component Analysis

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1 INTRODUCTION

The objective of the proposed method is to offer a qualitative estimate of the magnitude of felt earthquakes (occurring globally) for which location and magnitude are not rapidly available. This estimate is based on the surface area of the felt region and is derived from LastQuake app-launches. This method answers a specific need of the EMSC's rapid public information system. Indeed, with an ever-growing number of LastQuake app users, EMSC detects, through surges in app-launches, small magnitude earthquakes (down to $M \sim 1$ in certain regions) for which earthquake parameters (location and magnitude) may not be available for many hours or even days. We, therefore, aim at providing to our users qualitative information on the earthquake magnitude (small magnitude or not small magnitude) from the fastest data obtained: the location and time of LastQuake app-launches.

For the reasons presented below, it is not possible to make an accurate estimate of the magnitude from our dataset and our goal is more pragmatic: we aim at rapidly informing our users whether they have just felt a small-magnitude local earthquake or a more significant event. Once fully validated we plan to publish the results of this approach, named FAME (Felt Area for Magnitude Estimate), through our LastQuake system comprising a Twitter quakebot, a website for mobile devices and an app.

This development complements a study performed in the framework of the RISE project by Gianfranco Vanucci and Paolo Gasperini who exploited their method named BOXER to derive both magnitude and epicentral location from felt reports (Gasperini, et al., 1999; Gasperini, et al., 2010). The potential advantage of FAME being that it is, at least theoretically, faster.

2 DATA

The data exploited are LastQuake app-launches, i.e., the time and location when a user opened the LastQuake app. A surge in app-launches allows the rapid detection of felt earthquakes regardless of seismic data, as well as the mapping of the felt area (Bossu, et al., 2019). App-launches reflect information-seeking behaviour and are triggered by eyewitnesses feeling a tremor, thereby turning the eyewitnesses into near-real-time sensors (Bossu, et al., 2019). Indeed, the reaction time for app-launches is typically 20s (**Figure 2.1**).

The app-launches will be exploited in a time window ranging from 30 s before the trigger (before which an increase in app-launches is non-existent or very weak) and up to 150 s after the trigger. App-launches after the notification are disregarded as notifications themselves generate their own launches beyond the felt area. If a notification is published before the end of the estimation process, the process is stopped and no estimation is published.

Because there may be app-launches not linked to any tremor, especially in regions with a high density of LastQuake app users, geometric characteristics of the felt area will be evaluated using both app-launches and the local number of app users to limit the impact of outliers.

Figure 2.1: LastQuake app-launches related to the M4.4 earthquake in Los Angeles, California of Aug. 29th 2018 in (A) elapsed time from earthquake origin time vs. epicentral distance as well as (B) the same launch times corrected by P wave propagation times.

A second restriction concerns earthquakes that are close in time and space. In such cases, app-launches observed after the second event can be related to the first one or its notifications. Events preceding an earthquake by 3 hours and closer than 500 km must then be considered while proceeding to the qualitative estimation.

Finally, the estimation of the surface area of the felt region can only be correct when LastQuake app users geographically sample the felt area. This is not the case in coastal regions, or in deserts, mountainous or other sparsely populated regions. Rather than the surface area of the cluster defined by app-launches, several geometric parameters will be evaluated, such as the maximum elongation of the cluster.

3 OUTLINE OF THE FAME METHOD

FAME aims at the qualitative estimate of the magnitude of global felt earthquakes from the surface of the felt area as determined from LastQuake app-launches. The surface area of the felt region depends on three main factors: earthquake magnitude, hypocentral depth and seismic attenuation (Johnston, 1996; Frankel, 1994). In a region where the attenuation does not exhibit significant variations and earthquake depth is constrained in a limited range (e.g., in a region of crustal earthquakes only), it is then possible to estimate the magnitude from the surface area of the felt region using a regionally calibrated empirical relationship. Until now, this approach is usually restricted to historical earthquakes where instrumental measurements are not available and also includes intensity observations (Johnston, 1996).

The choice of a qualitative assessment is a pragmatic decision. First, covering the globe would require the establishment of many regionally calibrated empirical relationships linking the surface area of the felt region to instrumental magnitude. This time-consuming task will not solve the issue of how to treat subduction zones, for which earthquake depths can exhibit large variations. Rather than a quantitative magnitude estimate, FAME aims at discriminating small-magnitude earthquakes from more significant ones. Our assumption that the logarithm of the surface area of the felt region roughly depends on the earthquake magnitude, should work in all regions, even in subduction zones.

Figure 3.1: Time evolution of the surface area of the felt region as determined from LastQuake app-launches for three selected earthquakes of magnitude M2.9, M5.3 and M7.1 respectively. The felt area is estimated iteratively from 30s before the actual trigger.

The surface area of the felt region is not the only potential information of interest; its time evolution can also provide information about the size of the earthquake. For a small magnitude earthquake being only felt at short distances, there is no propagation effect as all eyewitnesses feel the tremor at basically the same time (**Figure 3.1**). This is not true for a M5 or larger event where the eyewitnesses located at the furthest distance from the epicentre feel the tremor several tens of seconds after its occurrence; this delay is increased to a couple of minutes for a major event (**Figure 3.1**). Time evolution will be used notably to evaluate when the evaluation of the surface area of the felt region is stable and then when the magnitude can be estimated.

4 METHOD

4.1 Felt area expansion

The app-launch locations are collected within a 500 km radius from the trigger location and until 150 s after the trigger time of an event. A mapping of 10 x 10 km² cells is performed around the trigger location (giving a 50-cell radius). At each time step, a cell is declared as active if there are at least N_{launches} app-launches and N_{install} app-installations within the cell and if the ratio $N_{\text{launches}}/N_{\text{install}}$ exceeds R . In practice, a trial-and-test process leads us to set N_{launches} , N_{install} and R equal to 2, 2 and 1 %, respectively. Also, if this ratio increases by 50 % between subsequent time steps, the cell is declared as active. The felt area is then estimated from the spatial distribution of the active cells. These parameters were manually adjusted by a trial-and-error procedure.

Figure 4.1 Example of major and minor axes of a convex-hull determined from the random location of A) 100, B) 50 and C) 150 points.

We choose to represent the felt area as a convex hull. The summits of convex hull are obtained using the `scipy.spatial.ConvexHull` object in Python (**Figure 4.1**). The maximum and minimum distances (L_{\max} , L_{\min}) between two opposite summits and the area are computed from the convex hull points. We also compute the parameter e analogous to the eccentricity of an ellipse as:

$$e = \sqrt{1 - L_{\min}^2 / L_{\max}^2}.$$

We then obtain the extent of the felt area from the app-launches data for past or current events (e.g., **Figure 4.6**).

4.2 Prediction model

We apply supervised machine learning, using the scikit-learn libraries of Python, in order to predict if an earthquake is small. The following features are used in the proposed model:

- the Flinn-Engdahl region and trigger location,
- the number of app-installations within a 500 km radius at the time of the trigger
- the number of app-launches following the trigger within a 500 km radius,
- the felt area expansion: maximum length, area and eccentricity
- the number of events that occurred less than 3 hours before the trigger and within a 500 km radius and the maximum magnitude of these events.
- the local time in hour (most recent classifiers)

The Flinn-Engdahl regions divide the Earth into seismic regions and are used within the EMSC services (Flinn & Engdahl, 1965; Flinn, et al., 1974). These regions were chosen as a supplement to the trigger location because the popularity of the LastQuake app depends on regions. The local time is used as a night/day indicator. Indeed, users can be expected to react differently depending on their activity at the instant of the event.

These features are pre-processed in order to build an efficient classifier. The records are split into a training set and a test set. The features of the training set are first scaled between -1 and 1, then a first selection is done based on the variance in order to remove features that have little variability. Next a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is performed to reduce the number of features to a lower dimensional space (Halko, et al., 2009). The same transformations are applied to the test set, such that a certain raw-value gives the same transformed value in the training and test sets even if the ranges of values are different.

An earthquake is classified as small if its magnitude is lower than a certain threshold, here fixed at 4. Since the relationship between the above features and the magnitude is non-linear, we use a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) classifier (Hinton, 1990; Glorot & Bengio, 2010). One of the advantages of the MLP is its capability to learn models in real-time implementation, i.e., on-line learning. Several tests were performed to choose the appropriate parameters of the classifier. The use of the 'SGD' solver allows a real-time implementation. The classifier is made of three hidden layers of 100 neurons each.

The primary classifier is built by learning from 2419 events from 2015 to June 2021, with magnitudes ranging from 0.4 to 7.5 (**Figure 4.2**). The dataset is split so that 60% of the data is part of the training set and 20% of the data is part of the test set. We have chosen the low ratio of data for the test set because of the small quantity of available data. The resultant classifier is referenced as the "without synthetic" classifier and has a precision of 91.9% (version 20210625121804). Another classifier is also built learning from the same past events and 2419×20 synthetics. There are 20 synthetics that are built for each past event by adding a Gaussian error to the number of launches, the maximum size, the area and the eccentricity of the felt area. The resultant progression should remain increasing, except for the eccentricity. Error percentages are set to 5, 10, 5 and 10 % for the number of launches, the maximum size, the eccentricity and the area, respectively. These percentages reflect the relative expected errors on these features. The resultant classifier, referenced as the "with synthetics" classifier, has a precision of 92.5% (version 20210625121804).

Figure 4.2 Distribution of the feature values of the initial dataset of 2419 earthquakes from 2015 to June 2021. **A)** the 15 most recurrent Flinn-Engdahl regions. **B)** The magnitude. **C)** The depth (km). **D)** The number of app-launches within a 500 km radius and 150 s after the earthquake. **E)** Number of prior earthquake within a 500 km radius that occurred less than 3 hours ago and **F)** Maximum magnitude of these prior earthquakes. **G)** Maximum length, **H)** surface and **I)** eccentricity of the felt region estimated from app-launches monitoring at 150 s after the trigger.

4.3 Real-time implementation

4.3.1 Classifier update

As we continuously collect data, we need to regularly update our classifiers. For now, we update the classifiers from scratch each time because we would like to have metrics on the first models in order to find out bugs and dysfunctions.

Later we should use the MLP classifier particularity that allows updating in near real-time. Indeed, the more data we will have collected, the more expensive (memory and time) it will be to update the classifier from scratch. The in-line update will then allow the classifier to be rapidly updated and we could delay large updates that re-compute the pre-processing parameters.

4.3.2 Predictions

In near real-time, the expansion data of the felt area as used by the classifier is not complete. Therefore, future data to come are replaced by -1 before parsing to the classifiers every 10 s in near real-time (Table 1). The classifier gives the probability of being small. We set a threshold so that a probability greater than or equal to 0.5 means that the event is probably small.

Table 1 Data passed to the classifier in a near real-time for a unique event (here app-trigger *rTXiRA*). Each row is passed to the classifier when the time in the first column is reached. Additional -1 values are replaced at each time step. B&H means Bosnia And Herzegovina.

Time since trigger [s]	Unchanging features							#launches								max dist. [km]			eccentricity			area [km2]		
	trglat	trglon	region	#install	histo	maxmag	local hour	-30	-20	-10	+0	+10	+20	...	+150	-30	...	+150	-30	...	+150	-30	...	+150
-30	43.467	17.599	B&H	289427	1	2.2	17.45	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	...	-1	0	...	-1	0	...	-1	0	...	-1
-20	43.467	17.599	B&H	289427	1	2.2	17.45	0	13	-1	-1	-1	-1	...	-1	0	...	-1	0	...	-1	0	...	-1
-10	43.467	17.599	B&H	289427	1	2.2	17.45	0	13	31	-1	-1	-1	...	-1	0	...	-1	0	...	-1	0	...	-1
0	43.467	17.599	B&H	289427	1	2.2	17.45	0	13	31	50	-1	-1	...	-1	0	...	-1	0	...	-1	0	...	-1
10	43.467	17.599	B&H	289427	1	2.2	17.45	0	13	31	50	65	-1	...	-1	0	...	-1	0	...	-1	0	...	-1
20	43.467	17.599	B&H	289427	1	2.2	17.45	0	13	31	50	65	78	...	-1	0	...	-1	0	...	-1	0	...	-1
...
150	43.467	17.599	B&H	289427	1	2.2	17.45	0	13	31	50	65	78	...	266	0	...	283	0	...	0.3079	0	...	10438

The classification of partial expansion was tested on past events and the success rate was calculated (Figure 4.3). The colours indicate which classifier we use (without or with synthetics). Of course, this result is biased by the fact we use the same data to learn and test. Then more statistics from real-time cases are waiting to measure the real accuracy of the process.

Figure 4.3: Success rate of the model as a function of (A) the monitoring delay and (B) the magnitude.

Globally, the success rate increases with the monitoring time (**Figure 4.3(A)**) and the classifier that includes synthetics is more efficient. The success rate, however, drops for magnitudes close to the magnitude threshold (4.0, **Figure 4.3(B)**). This bias is perhaps due the threshold itself because of uncertainty on magnitude but surely because of attenuation effects. The bias around the magnitude threshold should decrease when new events to learn the classifier have been added.

Figure 4.4: Evaluation of the probability confidence considering that an event is small if the probability exceeds (A) 0.5 and (B) 0.70.

These success rates illustrate the interest of giving a score to the predictions. This score s_{conf} is the sum of the confidence s_{proba} provided by the probability itself and the confidence s_{var} provided by the probability variance. The further the probability is away from the probability threshold (small ≥ 0.5 , not small < 0.5) the more this prediction is reliable (**Figure 4.4**). The lower the variance is, the more the prediction is reliable. A decrease of the variance also indicates that the probability is becoming stable; the weights of these scores are set to 0.5/0.5. A prediction curve can then be built step by step (**Figure 4.7**).

In practice we consider a prediction sufficiently stable to be published if:

- the probability confidence exceeds 0.85;
- the score exceeds 0.85; and
- the probability difference to the probability computed in the previous step is lower than 0.05.

Here are some examples of the use of the confidence score in case of a stable probability, i.e., the variance score is high ($s_{\text{var}} = \sim 1$). If the probability is very high or very low, the probability confidence is very high ($s_{\text{proba}} = \sim 1$), and then the confidence score is high ($s_{\text{conf}} = (1 + 1) \times 0.5 = 1$). However, if the probability is very close to 0.5, the probability confidence tends to 0, and then the confidence score is low ($s_{\text{conf}} = (0 + 1) \times 0.5 = 0.5$).

4.4 Example of an event of magnitude 3.3 in the Greater Los Angeles Area

A traffic surge (peak in the number of app-launches) was detected on 03/07/2021 at 08:23:00 UTC in the Greater Los Angeles Area (California, USA; trigger id *FBA7d0*), which was the consequence of a **small** earthquake of magnitude 3.3 that occurred 35 s earlier (**Figure 4.5**, event id: 1005968). The app-notification appeared at 08:25:0, i.e., 121 s after the trigger. App-launches were collected every 10 s, before and after the trigger, in order to build the felt area expansion curves (**Figure 4.6**).

Figure 4.5: Felt-map of the earthquake of magnitude 3.3, which is associated to the trigger FBA7d0. (<https://www.emsc-csem.org/Earthquake/earthquake.php?id=1005968>)

The felt-area maximum length and the felt-area surface rapidly reached a plateau and remained stable until the notification was sent. After the notification time, i.e., for monitoring delays greater than 121 s, an increase in the felt-area is observed (**Figure 4.6A-B**) because LastQuake users launched the app in response to the notification. In this example, we have estimated the felt-area expansion up to 150 s after the trigger. In practice, however, the prediction process is stopped once the notification is sent and the last increase is not included in the prediction.

Figure 4.6: Felt-area expansion associated to trigger FBA7d0. (A) Major and minor axis length of the area. (B) Surface of the area. (C) Eccentricity of the area. The grey patch starts at the notification time associated to this trigger.

The prediction curves are obtained from this felt-area expansion (Figure 4.7). Until 60 s after the trigger, this event does not seem to be small if only the probability is considered. However, the score of the prediction (0.81) remains lower than the value required to validate and publish the prediction, i.e., 0.85 (Figure 4.7C). Then the prediction process continues until all requirements are fulfilled, 100 s after the trigger. At this time, the event is predicted to be small with a probability of 1.0 and a score of 0.99. Ten seconds earlier, the score was only 0.68 and then the prediction was not validated, despite the fact that the probability of being small reached 1.0.

One should note that the absolute area given by the convex-hull is under-estimated in regards of the length of the major and minor axes. This is because of our definition of the major and minor axes, which are defined as the maximum and minimum distance between two opposite summits of the convex hull (Figure 4.1). However, the classifier is doing relative comparisons in order to predict if the earthquake is small or not small. The error on this convex-hull area should be corrected later.

Figure 4.7: Evolution of the prediction associated to trigger FBA7d0. (A) Probability of being small. (B) Variance of the probability including only the 4last probability estimations. (C) Score of the prediction. Grey patches highlight the domains where the prediction cannot be validated.

In the present case, then, the prediction was validated 100 s after the trigger and then could have been given about 135 s after the earthquake. In this specific test case, the earthquake magnitude and depth are rapidly known (155 s after the earthquake). Then the prediction is not needed any more. However, such low prediction delays (about 2 min) remain interesting when the magnitude and location of an event are obtained late.

5 PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The evaluation of the method is divided into the evaluation of the classifier, which will be updated regularly, and the evaluation of the real-time performance. The real-time performance will be statistically evaluated from the monitoring delay and the success rate.

The reader should remember that this prediction process is running in near real-time only since the beginning of July 2021. Until the end of August, many adjustments of the parameters and processes were performed in order to improve the process and results. Hence, the results, which are shown here, are to be considered as results for demonstration only. We hope, though, that the main trial-and-test phase is finished and that we soon will be able to provide statistically relevant data to discuss.

5.1 Classifier

Each classifier is scored using the testing test. The metrics are:

- the accuracy $A = (T_{\text{small}} + T_{\text{not-small}})/N_{\text{tests}}$ gives the proportion of correct predictions,
- the precision $P = T_{\text{small}}/(T_{\text{small}} + T_{\text{not-small}})$ gives the proportion of correct predictions of an event to be considered as small among all correct predictions,
- the recall $R = T_{\text{small}}/(T_{\text{small}} + F_{\text{not-small}})$ gives the proportion of correct predictions of an event to be considered as small among all small-magnitude events,
- the F1-score: $F_1 = 2RP/(R + P)$ gives the compromise between precision and recall.

where T_{small} and $T_{\text{not-small}}$ are the numbers of correct predictions and F_{small} and $F_{\text{not-small}}$ are the number of incorrect predictions for small-magnitude and not small-magnitude and N_{tests} is the number of events in the test set. The classifier is efficient, when data are collected from -30 to 150 s around the trigger time, with an accuracy and a F1 score greater than 90 % (**Figure 5.1**). In practice, i.e., in real-time, the prediction should be published as soon as possible in order to quickly reassure the users. The criteria to decide if the prediction has become stable (Section 4.3.2) allows publication sooner than after 150 s, but these early predictions reduce the accuracy of the classifier (Section **Feil! Fant ikke referansekinden.**).

5.2 Near real-time

The performance of the service is measured by the number of accurate predictions compared to the total number of predictions. At the time of this report, the success rate of the predictions is 67 % (**Figure 5.2**). Among incorrect predictions, 11 large-magnitude earthquakes were incorrectly predicted as being of small magnitude.

Last model: Wed, 01 Sep 2021 @ 10:06UTC
F1-score: 94.20%

Figure 5.1 Metrics of the classifiers: (A) number of events used to learn (excluding duplicates), (B) accuracy, (C) precision, (D) recall and (E) F1 score of the classifiers. Dashed light-grey lines indicate major updates.

All: 56 days 09:19:52.546509

03-Sep-2021@08:10 UTC

Figure 5.2 Success of the predictions. Correct predictions are shown in blue and incorrect predictions in orange. Bright colours show event predicted as small earthquakes, and light colours show the events not predicted as small.

In addition to success rates, figures are drawn to highlight where the service fails (**Figure 5.3** and **Figure 5.4**). In this report, we have chosen to show the magnitude as a function of the local time and the event depth only. The local time is interesting as users might react differently depending on their activity. The current night/day-time distribution is 0.37/0.63 (**Figure 5.3**). The depth has a strong impact on the success rate, since a deep earthquake is not felt in the same way as a shallow earthquake. Currently, 84 % of the earthquakes are located shallower than 25 km depth (**Figure 5.4**). Furthermore, the depth is not known by the classifier.

Figure 5.3 Magnitude of events with FAME prediction as a function of the local time. The magnitude threshold is shown at $M4$ by the horizontal black line. Incorrect predictions are shown in orange, correct predictions in blue. The penultimate and last predictions are shown by a diamond and a star, respectively.

Figure 5.4 Magnitude of events with FAME prediction as a function of the event depth. The magnitude threshold is shown at $M4$ by the vertical black line. Incorrect predictions are shown in orange, correct predictions in blue. The penultimate and last predictions are shown by a diamond and a star, respectively.

6 DISCUSSION

6.1 Specific cases

6.1.1 $M2.5$ in Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2021/08/25

We would like to describe a specific case in order to demonstrate the efficiency of the model and the interest of using a non-linear model. An earthquake of magnitude 2.5 occurred in Bosnia and Herzegovina on 25th August 2021 at 15:27:10 (<https://www.emsc-csem.org/Earthquake/earthquake.php?id=1028169#summary>).

A surge of app-launches started about 10 s after the earthquake time (t_0) and was detected 20 s later (t_0+30 s). A successful prediction was sent one minute after the origin time. Finally, the EMSC get the location and magnitude of this earthquake more than 10 minutes later.

Figure 6.1 Trigger rTXiRA, event id 1028169: (A) location of the app -launches within 120 s of start-up time of the app-traffic peak. The location of the earthquake was not known yet. (B) location of the felt reports associated to the earthquake including earthquake location available approximately 10 mins after the origin time

The maximum length of the area, in which the Lastquake app was launched, is about 300 km (**Figure 6.1A**). App-launches northwest of the map are in Croatia, where the Lastquake app is very popular. However, the felt reports were mostly located within 50 km of the earthquake's epicentre, in Bosnia and Herzegovina (**Figure 6.1B**).

These two distinct distances can also be found while performing the real-time prediction (**Figure 6.2B**). Indeed, while the increase in the number of app-launches seems to be constant (**Figure 6.2B**), we can observe that there are two plateaus for the felt area dimensions (**Figure 6.2B**). The first one starts at 20 s at around 50 km and the second appears at 60 s at around 280 km. The prediction is validated 10 s after the beginning of the first plateau, with a high confidence score (**Figure 6.2D**). The confidence score and the probability of being an event of small magnitude then decreases for the second plateau (**Figure 6.2C-D**).

The existence of the link between the app-launches in Croatia and this event can be questioned, because of:

- the presence of the felt reports only within 50 km from the earthquake epicentre;
- the location of the app-launches in Croatia farther than 100 km from the epicentre;
- the decrease of the probability of being a small magnitude event as well as the decreasing confidence score; and
- the propensity of the Croatian population to launch the LastQuake App at any time.

The model detected the anomaly (decrease of the probability and confidence score) and was able to correctly classify the event as being of small magnitude. We therefore conclude that following this approach is worthwhile.

Penultimate prediction 2021-08-25@15:28:10UTC: rTXiRA
Associated to evid 1028169: M2.4, Bosnia And Herzegovina

26-Aug-2021@11:01 UTC

Figure 6.2 Summary of the prediction for the app-trigger rTXiRA, which is associated to an earthquake in Bosnia and Herzegovina. (A) Evolution of the number of app-launches within 500 km from the trigger location. (B) Evolution of the felt area dimensions. (C) Evolution of the probability of being small. (D) Evolution of the confidence of the prediction. The cyan vertical lines show when the prediction was validated and sent.

6.1.2 M5.6 in the Philippines, 2021/08/27

The difficulty of correctly classifying if an earthquake is small increases in specific areas such as islands or deserts. The 4.6 magnitude earthquake that occurred on Friday, 27 August 2021 in the Philippines (event id 1028771: <https://www.emsc-csem.org/Earthquake/earthquake.php?id=1028799>) is a good example of LastQuake users being unequally distributed (Figure 6.3). Indeed, we clearly observe several plateaus in the felt area increase due to the distribution of users (Figure 6.4B), despite the fact that the increase of the cumulative number of app-launches is smoother (Figure 6.4A).

A)

B)

Figure 6.3 Trigger C8jzcK, event id 1028771: (A) location of the app-launches within 120 s of start time of the app-traffic peak. The location of the earthquake was not known yet. (B) location of the felt reports associated to the earthquake.

Last prediction 2021-08-27@10:25:15UTC: C8jzcK
Associated to evid 1028771: M5.6, Mindanao, Philippines

27-Aug-2021@11:40 UTC

Figure 6.4 Summary of the prediction for the app-trigger C8jzcK, which is associated to an earthquake in the Philippines. (A) Evolution of the number of app-launches within 500 km from the trigger location. (B) Evolution of the felt area dimensions. (C) Evolution of the probability of being small. (D) Evolution of the confidence of the prediction. The cyan vertical lines show when the prediction was validated and sent.

6.2 General observations

One item to investigate is that there are more incorrect predictions concerning large magnitude earthquakes than small magnitude events (**Figure 5.2**). We cannot yet fully explain this behaviour, but the asymmetric distribution of earthquake magnitudes (independently of the prediction process) may have an influence on the learning and thus on the success rate of the predictions. Indeed, it is known from global earthquake studies and the Gutenberg-Richter relation that more small magnitude earthquakes occur than large magnitude earthquakes (85 % during the test phase). Despite the fact that strong earthquakes are felt more intensively than small earthquakes, their lower number is such that more small magnitude earthquakes are felt (65%) than large magnitude earthquakes during the test phase.

The local time should not influence the success rate of the predictions (**Figure 5.3**) because the local time is taken into account by the classifier. However, there are less app-triggers in the night than in the day. This might later introduce a bias in predictions. Up to now, this has no visible effects. Indeed, there is almost the same proportion of correct predictions in the day and in the night.

The Croatian app-launches during the Bosnia and Herzegovina earthquake represent outliers for the prediction process. Indeed, a clustering algorithm, such as DBSCAN (e.g., Fayjaloun, et al., 2020; Zhong, et al., 2016), may be added in order to eliminate outliers from the distribution of app-launches. However, new tests with this selection must be performed in order to measure the benefits of this addition. On the other hand, by incorporating these random outliers, the classifier learns to recognize exceptions within a data set.

We voluntarily do not specify the magnitude scale that is used for learning. Indeed, magnitudes are used as they are provided in the EMSC services and can be of several types (M_w , local, m_b , M_S ...). This choice was made because the process is not expected to predict magnitudes, but only provide fast qualitative information: is the earthquake small or not, if the magnitude is below or above a certain threshold (moment magnitude of 4). Furthermore, magnitude differences with moment magnitude range from -0.6 to 0.78 for magnitudes around 4 considering the relationships given by Wason et al. (2012), Lolli, et al. (2014) and Cara, et al. (2017). This error interval can partially explain the drop of the success rate around M4 (**Figure 4.3B**). This drop in the success rate will potentially disappear when including a larger number of events in the learning process.

7 CONCLUSIONS

We aim to estimate qualitatively whether a felt earthquake is of small magnitude, even before knowing its location. To this end, we employ the number and location of the LastQuake app-launches immediately after an earthquake. The analysis of the data coming from the app traffic surge allows the geometry of the felt area to be estimated. Deep learning is then used in order to build a classifier.

The project is now at the end of its trial-and-test phase and first results are encouraging. However, we cannot yet prove the efficiency of the estimate. Due to the small quantity of data gathered in the test phase, it will take further time before reaching success rates that allow the estimates to be published. This gives us time to think about how we could publish the estimates based on the accuracy of our model.

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